

Pulsed Power Evaluation and Simulation of High Voltage 4H-SiC P-Type SGTOs

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Abstract— Future Army pulsed power applications semiconductor devices that will meet requirements for high-power, low weight and volume, and fast switching speed. The following paper presents the pulsed power evaluation of high voltage silicon carbide (SiC) super gate turn-off (SGTO) thyristors. These devices are well suited for high voltage, high temperature pulsed power and continuous power electronic systems. A pulse-forming network (PFN) circuit and a low inductance, series resistor-capacitor (LRC) circuit were developed to evaluate both the fast di/dt capability and the pulse safe operating area (SOA) of the SiC SGTO. Transient simulations of the high voltage SiC SGTOs were also performed on a narrow pulse LRC circuit to investigate the device's switching behavior under extreme pulsed conditions.

Keywords—Silicon carbide; Gate Turn-off Thyristor; Pulsed power; pulse-forming network; safe operating area

I. INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide's (SiC's) enhanced material properties are paving the path for next generation power devices that will be used in various power electronics and pulsed power applications [1-3]. The Army pulsed power systems require the power devices to operate at fast speeds, high temperature, and high power density. SiC has various attractive properties compared to its silicon counterpart. Silicon carbide's material properties advantages such as a high critical field, high saturation velocity, high thermal conductivity, high energy bandgap, large elastic modulus makes it extremely favorable for pulse switching systems and applications [1-4]. Due to its excellent conductivity modulation capability, Super-gate turn-off thyristors (SGTOs) are well suited for multiple applications that require fast di/dt switching at extremely high peak current levels. The U.S. Army Research Laboratory (ARL) is interested in understanding the switching behavior of high power silicon carbide bipolar devices subjected to elevated current densities at unique time-scales in the microsecond and millisecond regime through modeling and simulation. Accurate physics-based SiC models and simulations are extremely essential and will enable better

optimization of SiC device designs leading to enhanced device performance.

This work presents the pulse power evaluation and numerical transient simulation of high voltage SiC SGTO thyristors. The SGTOs evaluated in this paper are subjected to two different switching conditions. The transient simulations were performed utilizing a physics-based, technology computer aided design software. The simulation investigates the fast di/dt switching capabilities of the SGTO in a narrow pulse LRC circuit.

II. DEVICE STRUCTURE

The SGTO devices investigated in this research were designed and fabricated by Wolfspeed, a Cree Company. The SGTOs have asymmetrical structures enabling a forward blocking capability of 10 kV and 15 kV. The forward blocking capability of the SGTO is primarily dependent on the thickness and doping concentration of the drift region of the device. The cross-sections of the SGTOs are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. These devices were fabricated on an 350 μm n+ SiC substrate. This resulted in the SiC SGTOs having the anode terminal on the topside and cathode terminal on the bottom side. These devices were also designed to have very high turn-on gain. A p-type buffer layer doped approximately $5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, 4 μm thick was grown on a SiC substrate. Low doped, p-layer of 90 μm (10 kV SGTO) and 120 μm (15 kV SGTO) was grown. The doping of the drift layer for both devices were within $2 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Following this was the growth of n-type base layer, doped at approximately $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The thickness of the base layer was 2 μm . Lastly, a heavily doped ($>1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) p+ anode layer of thickness 2 μm was grown. Further design details of the devices characterized and evaluated in this research has been published by Wolfspeed and ARL and can be found in the following references [3-5].

Fig. 1. Cross-section view of 10 kV, 1.0 cm² SiC Super-GTO. Note: the gate is anode referenced in SiC SGTO.

Fig. 2. Cross-section view of 15 kV, 1.0 cm² SiC Super-GTO. Note: the gate is anode referenced in SiC SGTO.

III. DEVICE EVALUATION

A low inductance, series resistor-capacitor (LRC) circuit and pulse-forming network (PFN) circuit were developed to evaluate the fast di/dt capability and the narrow pulse safe operating area (SOA) of the SiC SGTO.

A. LRC Circuit

The pulse circuit implemented to analyze the fast di/dt capability of the SiC SGTOs was a low inductance, series resistor-capacitor topology depicted in Fig. 3. The circuit inductance distribution was reduced by using a wide anti-parallel bussing configuration between the capacitor and the load. A low capacitance, Maxwell energy storage capacitor rated for 150 nF and used for rapid, high-current discharge was used to briefly store the charge voltage before the SGTO was triggered into the ON-state. The circuit load was comprised of HVR large-area bulk ceramic disk resistors designed to withstand high power and high energy.

Fig. 3. Low inductance, series resistor-capacitor circuit schematic for evaluating the fast di/dt characteristics of the SiC SGTOs

B. PFN Circuit

An automated pulse forming circuit unit was developed to evaluate the long-term reliability and safe operating area of high voltage SiC SGTOs at a 100 μ s square pulse-width at 0.5 Hz rate, creating more I^2t stress in the devices. The PFN was developed from discrete inductors and capacitors in order to generate the 100 μ s full width half-maximum (FWHM) pulse used to evaluate the SiC SGTOs' pulse switching characteristics. The 10-stage Rayleigh pulse forming network was matched to a 0.5 Ω load which provides the 100 μ s pulses. The PFN has a total capacitance of 85 μ F and can be charged to 15 kV for a maximum pulse energy of 9.563 kJ. A simplified circuit schematic of the PFN is shown in Fig. 4. An expanded description of the system can be found in the following references [6-8].

Fig. 4. Simplified 10 stage PFN schematic for evaluating the long term reliability and safe operating area characteristics of the SiC SGTOs

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section highlights the switching characteristics of the SGTO devices when implemented in a LRC and PFN circuit topology. The spreading velocity is the rate at which the plasma spreads across the area of the thyristor. This device parameter is essential for determining the switching rate of the SGTO and the maximum di/dt capability of the SGTO. The turn-on delay of the SGTO is affected by increasing the gate current. For the maximum di/dt characterization of the 10 kV and 15 kV SGTO, a peak gate current of 400A/ μ s was used to drastically reduce to turn-on delay, which accelerates the conductivity modulation process in the device, maximizing the peak current flowing through the device at a given charge voltage.

A. 10 kV SiC GTO

The maximum peak di/dt achieved with the 10 kV SiC SGTO utilizing the LRC is illustrated in Fig. 5. The di/dt was 11 kA/ μ s measured across the 10-90% ratio of the peak

current pulse. The maximum peak current attained with the 10 kV SiC SGTO in the LRC circuit was 1.830kA (2.5 kA/cm²). At 1.830kA, the device approached saturation in the LRC circuit due to the fast rate of current rise at the current level.

Fig. 5. Maximum di/dt capability of the 10 kV SGTO. the peak di/dt in LRC circuit was reached at a current amplitude of 1830 A. The di/dt measured from 10-90% of maximum current level was 11 kA/ μ s.

A safe operating area level with respect to peak pulsed current with a FWHM pulse-width of 100 μ s was established with the 10 kV, SiC SGTOs at a peak current of 2.0 kA (Fig. 6). This device achieved over 100,000 pulses at a nominal current level of 2.0 kA. The current rising edge di/dt was 0.350 kA/ μ s at 2 kA. It is important to note that the current rise edge was not limited by the SiC SGTO but by the output inductance of the PFN design. the device performed reliably without any significant degradation at pulsed current levels up to 2.0 kA (Fig. 6). At peak current levels above 2.0 kA, an abrupt shift in the device forward voltage was observed. It was believed that the forward voltage shift was attributed to the device over-heating and thermal runaway. The increased peak power and peak energy dissipation in the SGTO above 2 kA ultimately lead to the catastrophic failure of the device.

Fig. 6. 2.0 kA pulse current discharge in 10 kV SGTO utilizing a 10 stage PFN Circuit

B. 15 kV SiC GTO

The thicker epilayer thickness of the 15 kV SGTO compared to the 10kV SiC SGTO increases the turn-on delay and on-resistance, which reduces the di/dt and peak current handling capability of the device as shown in Fig. 7. The maximum peak di/dt achieved with the 15 kV SiC SGTO utilizing the LRC circuit is illustrated in Fig. 7. The di/dt was 8kA/ μ s measured across the 10-90% ratio of the peak current pulse of 1.37 kA (2.6kA/cm²). At 1.370 kA, the device approached its current saturation limit in the LRC circuit due to the current rate of rise time (di/dt).

Fig. 7. Maximum di/dt capability of 15 kV SGTO: the peak di/dt in LRC circuit was reached at a current amplitude of 1370 A. The di/dt measured from 10-90% of maximum current level was 8 kA/ μ s.

The baseline peak current level of 2 kA with a 100 μ s square pulse-width was used to access the safe operating area level of the 15 kV, SiC SGTOs as shown in Fig. 8. The 15 kV SGTO device achieved over 70,000 pulses at a nominal current level of 2.0 kA, however it degraded drastically, implying that the SOA for the 15 kV devices is less than 2 kA.. The failure modes are similar to those observed with the 10 kV SiC SGTO and has been recently published in [8].

Fig. 9. 2.0 kA pulse current discharge in 15kV SGTO utilizing a 10 stage PFN Circuit

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

As mentioned previously, the gate current affects the turn-on delay of the GTO. Fig. 10 illustrates the gate current comparison as a function of the gate resistor. The series gate resistance used on the SGTO ranged from 10 Ω , 1.5 Ω , and 0.75 Ω . These gate resistors corresponded to peak applied gate currents of 10 A, 64 A, and 128 A, respectively. The gate current rise rate at 10 ohm (10 A peak) was 200 A/ μ s, while the gate current rise rate rising at 1.5 ohm (64 A peak) and 0.75 Ω (128 A peak) was approximately 400 A/ μ s. Fig. 10 shows that simulated gate current rising edge results agrees fairly well with the experimental results.

Fig. 10. Experimental v. Simulation of the rising edge of different gate drive currents used to determine minimum turn-on delay.

Fig. 11 depicts simulation of 10 kV SiC SGTO as a function of gate resistance. The simulation was done with a charge voltage of 3 kV. The simulated results show that the SGTO is triggered-on slightly faster when utilizing a low gate resistance. Furthermore, the variation in peak current is approximately 153A between the gate resistance of 10 Ω and 0.75 Ω .

Fig. 11. 10 kV SiC SGTO simulation of the turn-on delay as a function of gate resistance

VI. CONCLUSION

The fast di/dt capability of the high-voltage SiC SGTOs was evaluated in a narrow-pulse LRC circuit, and their long-term pulse power reliability was determined using an automated pulse forming network system that generates a 100 μ s pulse-width. The robustness and the fast di/dt handling capability of the devices presented in this research prove that SiC is an excellent candidate for pulsed power applications.

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